

Plexiform Ameloblastoma- A Rare Case Report

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A 22-year-old female patient reported to the Department of Oral Medicine and Radiology of Kothiwal Dental College and Research Centre with a complain of swelling in right side of the face since 1 month.

Swelling was associated with pain. Pain was gradual in onset, moderate in intensity, intermittent in nature.

No aggravating and relieving factors. Eventually pain was associated with pus discharge which increased on chewing and subsides on itself.

Medical, Dental, and personal history was unremarkable.

Clinical examination- On inspection the swelling was extending from right ala of nose to inferior border of mandible superio-inferiorly and from commissure of the lip to angle of the mouth antero-posteriorly measuring about 5cm x 7cm in diameter. Overlying skin appeared tensed and shiny (figure 1 and 2).

Figure 1- Extraoral- Frontal view.

Figure 2 – Extraoral- lateral view

Figure 3-Intraoral view

On palpation swelling was soft to firm in consistency, non-tender, non-compressible and non-reducible in nature, while palpating egg shell crackling was truly appreciated. No lymph nodes were palpable.

Intraoral examination- Swelling present on right alveolar region of size- 5cm x 3cm approximately extending Antero-posteriorly- from distal aspect of canine to mesial aspect of 48 and Bucco-lingually-from depth of the buccal vestibule to lingual sulcus (figure 3).

On intraoral palpation the swelling was firm to hard in consistency, non-tender, non-palpable, non-reducible and non-compressible but while palpating, purulent discharge was noticed from the swelling. Based on the history and clinical examination the provisional diagnosis was made as Ameloblastoma with respect to Right mandible.

The differential diagnosis was made as-

- 1- Odontogenic Keratocyst
- 2- Odontogenic Myxoma
- 3- Central giant cell granuloma
- 4- CEOT

Investigations-

1. OPG- OPG reveals Multilocular radiolucency (with intertwining thin radio-opaque septae) extending anteroposteriorly from 42 to 48 and superoinferiorly from alveolar crest to lower border of mandible. Small locules can be seen on the mesial aspect suggestive of Honey comb appearance and large locules can be seen on the distal aspect suggestive of Soap bubble appearance (figure 4).

Figure 4- OPG

Figure 5- CBCT

2. CBCT- Cone beam computed tomography further confirms OPG findings and revealed lesion causing slight ballooning expansion of the mandible with significant thinning of inferior cortices but intermittently intact with multiple small compartments (figure 5).

3. **FNAC** – Aspiration yielded an infected material i.e. pus mixed with blood (figure 6).

Figure 6- FNAC

4. **Incisional Biopsy**- It reveals Ameloblastic epithelium in an interconnecting strands and cords over a background of mature fibrous connective tissue stroma. Ameloblastic epithelium demonstrates peripheral columnar cells with palisaded hyperchromatic nucleus and central star shaped stellate reticulum like cells. The connective tissue stroma shows loosely arranged collagen fibers in association with fibroblast and infiltration of diffused chronic inflammatory cells predominantly consisting of lymphocytes and plasma cells (Figure 7).

Histopathological diagnosis was **Plexiform Ameloblastoma**.

Figure 7- Incisional Biopsy report

Management- This particular case was treated with Enucleation.

Various modalities of treatment have been suggested in literature like-

- Curettage
- Enucleation
- Marsupialization
- Cryosurgery
- Electrocautery
- Radical en bloc resection
- Sclerotherapy